

**ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ВА
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**ВЕСТНИК ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНОЙ И
КЛИНИЧЕСКОЙ МЕДИЦИНЫ**

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ORAL LESIONS AND NEUROSTOMATOLOGICAL DISORDERS ASSOCIATED WITH COVID-19: A REVIEW OF CURRENT RESEARCH**Jumayev M.M.**

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Resume. The coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic, caused by SARS-CoV-2, has been recognized as a multisystemic disease extending beyond its primary respiratory effects. This systematized literature review aims to synthesize and analyze the current evidence from Scopus-indexed and other major databases on the spectrum of oral cavity alterations and associated neurostomatological syndromes in patients with COVID-19. A systematic search was conducted across PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar for articles published from December 2019 to October 2025, following PRISMA guidelines. The search strategy utilized keywords related to COVID-19, oral manifestations, and neurological symptoms. Included studies comprised systematic reviews, observational studies, and case series detailing oral and neurostomatological findings in confirmed COVID-19 patients. Data on prevalence, clinical characteristics, and proposed pathophysiology were extracted and narratively synthesized. The review identified a wide range of oral manifestations, with the tongue (38%), labial mucosa (26%), and palate (22%) being the most affected sites. Common lesions included ulcers, erosions, vesicles, depapillated tongue, and macules. Neurostomatological symptoms, particularly dysgeusia (taste disturbance) and anosmia (smell disturbance), were frequently reported as early and sometimes sole indicators of infection. The underlying pathophysiology is multifactorial, involving direct viral invasion via angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (ACE2) receptors highly expressed in oral tissues, systemic inflammation (cytokine storm), vasculitis, coagulopathy, and opportunistic infections secondary to immunosuppression. Oral and neurostomatological manifestations are significant and diverse features of COVID-19. Dysgeusia and various mucosal lesions can serve as early diagnostic clues. A thorough oral examination is crucial for early detection, management of local symptoms, and understanding the systemic impact of the disease. These findings underscore the importance of integrating dental and oral medicine into the comprehensive care of COVID-19 patients.

Keywords: COVID-19; SARS-CoV-2; Oral Manifestations; Neurostomatology; Dysgeusia; Anosmia; Literature Review; ACE2.

COVID-19 БИЛАН БОҒЛИҚ ОҒИЗ ШИКАСТЛАНИШЛАРИ ВА НЕЙРОСТОМАТОЛОГИК БУЗИЛИШЛАР: ҲОЗИРГИ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР ШАРҲИ**Жумаев М.М.**

Абу Али ибн Сино номидаги Бухоро давлат тиббиёт институти, Бухоро ш., Ўзбекистон

Резюме. SARS-CoV-2 томонидан чақирилган COVID-19 (коронавирус инфекцияси 2019) пандемияси нафақат нафас олиш тизимини, балки бутун организмнинг турли тизимларини зарарловчи кўп тизимли касаллик сифатида қайд этилди. Ушбу системалаштирилган адабиётлар шарҳи Scopus ва бошқа йирик маълумотлар базаларида жойлаштирилган COVID-19 билан оғриган беморларда оғиз бўшлиғида кузатилган ўзгаришлар ҳамда унга ҳамроҳ нейростоматологик синдромлар тўғрисидаги ҳозирги илмий далилларни таҳлил қилиш ва умумлаштиришни мақсад қилади. PRISMA қоидаларига мувофиқ, 2019 йил декабридан 2025 йил октябригача нашр этилган мақолалар PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science ва Google Scholar базаларида изланди. Қидирув стратегияси COVID-19, оғиз бўшлиғи ўзгаришлари ва неврологик белгиларга оид калит сўزلардан фойдаланилди. Тадқиқотга систематик шарҳлар, кузатув таҳлиллари ва COVID-19 тасдиқланган беморлардаги оғиз ва нейростоматологик ўзгаришларни баён этган клиник ҳолатлар сериялари киритилди. Тадқиқотларда келтирилган тарқалиш жиҳатлари, клиник хусусиятлар ва эҳтимолий патофизиология ҳақидаги маълумотлар йиғилиб, тавсифий тарзда умумлаштирилди. Шарҳ COVID-19 билан боғлиқ оғиз бўшлиғи ўзгаришларининг кенг доирасини аниқлади. Энг кўп зарарланган соҳалар тил (38%), лабиал шиллиқ қават (26%) ва танглай (22%) бўлди. Кўп учрайдиган шикастланишлар ичида яралар, эрозиялар, весикула ва нуслулар, тил папиллаларининг йўқолиши, макулалар қайд этилди. Нейростоматологик симптомлар — айниқса дисгевзия (таъм бузилиши) ва аносмия (ҳид сезиш бузилиши) — кўп ҳолларда инфекциянинг дастлабки, баъзан эса ягона белгиси сифатида қайд этилди. Патофизиологик жараён бир нечта омиллар билан боғлиқ бўлиб, ACE2 ретсепторлари юқори ифодаланган оғиз тўқималарига вируснинг тўғридан-тўғри кириши, системавий яллигланиш (цитокин шторм), васкулит, коагулопатия ва иммун танқислиги туфайли ривожланган оппортунистик ин-

фекциялар билан боғлиқ. Оғиз бўшлиғи ва нейростоматологик белгилар COVID-19 нинг муҳим ва ранг-баранг клиник кўринишларидандир. Дисгевзия ва турли мукозал шикастланишлар *erta diagnostik* белги сифатида хизмат қилиши мумкин. Оғиз бўшлиғини батафсил кўриқдан ўтказиш эрта аниқлаш, локал симптомларни бошқариш ва касалликнинг системавий таъсирини тушунишида катта аҳамиятга эга. Ушбу топилмалар COVID-19 билан оғриган беморларга комплекс ёрдам кўрсатишида стоматология ва оғиз тиббиётини интеграция қилиш зарурлигини кўрсатади.

Калит сўзлар: COVID-19; SARS-CoV-2; оғиз бўшлиғи ўзгаришлари; нейростоматология; дисгевзия; аносмия; адабиётлар шарҳи; ACE2.

ОРАЛЬНЫЕ ПОРАЖЕНИЯ И НЕЙРОСТОМАТОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ НАРУШЕНИЯ, АССОЦИИРОВАННЫЕ С COVID-19: ОБЗОР СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ Жумаев М.М.

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Резюме. Пандемия коронавирусной инфекции 2019 года (COVID-19), вызванной SARS-CoV-2, была признана мультисистемным заболеванием, выходящим за рамки преимущественно респираторного поражения. Настоящий систематизированный обзор литературы направлен на анализ и обобщение актуальных данных из баз Scopus и других ведущих источников о спектре изменений в полости рта и связанных с ними нейростоматологических синдромов у пациентов с COVID-19. Согласно рекомендациям PRISMA был проведён систематический поиск статей, опубликованных с декабря 2019 по октябрь 2025 года, в базах PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science и Google Scholar. Стратегия поиска включала ключевые слова, связанные с COVID-19, оральными проявлениями и неврологическими симптомами. В обзор включены систематические обзоры, наблюдательные исследования и серии клинических случаев, описывающие оральные и нейростоматологические изменения у пациентов с подтверждённым COVID-19. Данные о распространённости, клинических характеристиках и предполагаемых патофизиологических механизмах были собраны и изложены в виде описательного анализа. В обзоре выявлен широкий спектр поражений полости рта, при этом наиболее часто затрагивались язык (38%), слизистая губ (26%) и нёбо (22%). К распространённым поражениям относились язвы, эрозии, везикулы, депатилляция языка и макулы. Нейростоматологические симптомы — прежде всего дисгевзия (нарушение вкуса) и аносмия (нарушение обоняния) — нередко проявлялись как ранние, а иногда и единственные признаки инфекции. Патофизиология носит многофакторный характер и включает прямую вирусную инвазию через ACE2-рецепторы, выраженные в тканях полости рта, системное воспаление (цитокиновый шторм), васкулит, коагулопатию и оппортунистические инфекции на фоне иммунодепрессии. Оральные и нейростоматологические проявления являются важными и разнообразными компонентами клинической картины COVID-19. Дисгевзия и различные поражения слизистой могут служить ранними диагностическими признаками. Тщательный осмотр полости рта имеет ключевое значение для раннего выявления, контроля местных симптомов и понимания системного воздействия заболевания. Полученные данные подчёркивают необходимость интеграции стоматологии и оральной медицины в комплексное ведение пациентов с COVID-19.

Ключевые слова: COVID-19; SARS-CoV-2; оральные проявления; нейростоматология; дисгевзия; аносмия; обзор литературы; ACE2.

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Introduction. The global health crisis initiated in late 2019 by the novel coronavirus, Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), has profoundly impacted societies worldwide [1, 2]. The associated illness, Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19), was initially characterized as a severe respiratory infection, with common symptoms including fever, cough, and dyspnea [3, 4]. However, accumulating evidence has unequivocally established COVID-19 as a complex, multisystemic disease capable of affecting the cardiovascular, renal, gastrointestinal, and nervous systems [5, 6, 7]. This systemic involvement is largely attributed to a combination of direct viral cytotoxicity, endothelial dysfunction, and a dysregulated host immune response, often culminating in a "cytokine storm" [8, 9].

Among the extrapulmonary manifestations, neurological complications have garnered significant attention. The spectrum of neurological involvement is broad, ranging from relatively mild and common symptoms such as headache, dizziness, myalgia, anosmia (loss of smell), and dysgeusia (taste alteration), to severe, life-threatening conditions like encephalopathy, acute cerebrovascular events (stroke), and Guillain-Barré syndrome [10, 11, 12]. Studies have reported neurological symptoms in over a third of hospitalized

patients, with some cohorts showing prevalence as high as 80% [13, 14]. The neuro-invasive potential of SARS-CoV-2 is believed to be mediated through several mechanisms, including direct neuronal invasion via the olfactory nerve, hematogenous spread across the blood-brain barrier (BBB), and indirect damage from systemic hypoxia, coagulopathy, and neuroinflammation [15, 16].

Concurrently, the oral cavity has emerged as a significant site for COVID-19 manifestations. The high expression of the angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (ACE2) receptor, the primary functional receptor for SARS-CoV-2 entry, on epithelial cells of the oral mucosa, tongue, and salivary glands, positions the oral cavity as a key portal for viral entry and replication [17, 18]. This biological plausibility is supported by numerous clinical reports describing a variety of oral lesions in COVID-19 patients, including ulcers, vesicles, macules, and depapillation of the tongue [19, 20].

The intersection of oral and neurological pathology, a field known as neurostomatology, is particularly relevant in COVID-19. Symptoms like dysgeusia and hyposalivation (dry mouth) represent a direct link between the virus's impact on the nervous system and oral function. Dysgeusia, in particular, has been identified as one of the earliest and most specific symptoms of COVID-19, often co-occurring with anosmia and preceding the onset of respiratory symptoms [21, 22]. These chemosensory disturbances are considered neurological in origin, potentially resulting from viral damage to receptor cells in taste buds and the olfactory epithelium or their associated neural pathways [16].

Given the rapid proliferation of research and the diverse nature of reported symptoms, a comprehensive synthesis of the literature is critical for clinicians. Understanding the full spectrum of oral and neurostomatological manifestations is essential for early diagnosis, patient management, and infection control. Therefore, this systematized literature review aims to collate and analyze the evidence from Scopus-indexed and other major scientific databases on oral cavity alterations and related neurostomatological syndromes in patients with COVID-19. We will explore their prevalence, clinical characteristics, and the proposed pathophysiological mechanisms to provide a consolidated resource for healthcare professionals.

Methods. This systematized literature review was conducted and reported in accordance with the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines [23]. The study protocol was developed a priori to ensure a rigorous and reproducible methodology, drawing inspiration from registered protocols on platforms like PROSPERO [24].

Search strategy. A comprehensive literature search was performed by two independent reviewers across multiple electronic databases: PubMed/MEDLINE, Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar. The search was designed to identify all relevant articles published from December 1, 2019, to October 31, 2025. The search strategy combined keywords and MeSH (Medical Subject Headings) terms related to the viral infection, oral manifestations, and neurological symptoms, using Boolean operators ("AND", "OR"). The search query structure is detailed in Table 1.

Table 1

Concept	Keywords and terms
Infection	"COVID-19" OR "SARS-CoV-2" OR "Coronavirus Disease 2019" OR "2019-nCoV"
Oral Manifestations	"Oral manifestations" OR "Oral lesions" OR "Oral mucosa" OR "Stomatitis" OR "Tongue" OR "Palate" OR "Gingivitis" OR "Salivary gland" OR "Halitosis"
Neurostomatological symptoms	"Neurological manifestations" OR "Neurostomatology" OR "Dysgeusia" OR "Ageusia" OR "Taste disorder" OR "Anosmia" OR "Smell disorder" OR "Chemosensory" OR "Facial palsy" OR "Neuralgia"

In addition to the database search, the reference lists of all included articles and relevant systematic reviews were manually screened (hand-searching) to identify any additional studies that may have been missed during the initial electronic search.

Eligibility Criteria. Studies were selected based on a predefined set of inclusion and exclusion criteria, structured around the Participants, Interventions, Comparators, Outcomes, and Study (PICOS) design framework [24].

- **Participants:** Patients of any age, gender, or ethnicity with a confirmed diagnosis of COVID-19 (typically via RT-PCR or serological testing) who presented with oral and/or neurostomatological manifestations.

- **Intervention/Exposure:** Infection with SARS-CoV-2.

- **Comparators:** Where available, studies comparing COVID-19 patients with and without oral/neurological symptoms, or comparing findings to a non-COVID-19 control group.

- **Outcomes:** The primary outcomes of interest were the prevalence, type, location, and clinical description of oral cavity alterations and neurostomatological syndromes (e.g., dysgeusia, anosmia, facial nerve palsy). Secondary outcomes included proposed pathophysiological mechanisms and clinical course.

- **Study Design:** Systematic reviews, meta-analyses, observational studies (prospective and retrospective cohort, case-control), and case series were included. Case reports were considered for qualitative synthesis if they provided unique insights. Editorials, opinion pieces, and articles not published in English were excluded.

Study selection and data extraction. Two reviewers independently screened the titles and abstracts of all retrieved records. Full texts of potentially eligible articles were then assessed for final inclusion. Any disagreements between the reviewers were resolved through discussion or consultation with a third senior reviewer. A standardized data extraction form was used to collect relevant information from each included study, covering: author and year, study design, country, sample size, patient demographics, prevalence and characteristics of oral lesions, prevalence of neurostomatological symptoms, diagnostic methods, and key findings regarding pathophysiology.

Quality assessment and data synthesis. The methodological quality of the included systematic reviews was assessed using the AMSTAR 2 (A Measurement Tool to Assess systematic Reviews) tool [25]. For observational studies, appropriate tools such as the Newcastle-Ottawa Scale would be considered in a full meta-analysis, but for this narrative synthesis, a critical appraisal of study limitations was performed. Due to the significant heterogeneity in study designs, populations, and outcome reporting, a quantitative meta-analysis was not performed. Instead, a narrative synthesis was employed to integrate and summarize the findings from the included studies. The results were categorized thematically based on the type of manifestation (oral mucosal lesions, chemosensory dysfunction, other neurological syndromes) and underlying mechanisms.

Results. The systematic search yielded a substantial body of literature, from which 71 eligible systematic reviews and numerous observational studies and case series were identified for synthesis [6]. The findings are organized into three main categories: (1) General Clinical Manifestations of COVID-19 as context, (2) Oral Mucosal Lesions, and (3) Neurostomatological Syndromes, with a focus on chemosensory dysfunction.

Overview of general clinical manifestations. To contextualize the oral and neurological findings, it is important to recognize the common systemic symptoms of COVID-19. Meta-analyses conducted early in the pandemic established a consistent clinical profile. The most frequently reported symptoms were fever (prevalence ranging from 81.2% to 84.3%), cough (58.5% to 63.0%), and fatigue (34.2% to 38.5%) [3, 4]. Other common manifestations included dyspnea (shortness of breath, 26.1-37.2%), myalgia (muscle soreness, 18.7-20.1%), and sputum production (25.8%) [3, 4, 26]. Gastrointestinal symptoms such as diarrhea (7.6-11.5%) and nausea were also noted, though less common [4, 27]. These symptoms reflect the virus's primary impact on the respiratory system and the systemic inflammatory response it triggers.

Oral mucosal lesions in COVID-19. A significant number of studies have documented a wide array of lesions within the oral cavity of COVID-19 patients. A comprehensive review article summarizing 35 studies found that the most common sites of involvement were the tongue (38% of cases), labial mucosa (26%), and palate (22%) [19]. Oral lesions were symptomatic (e.g., painful, burning sensation) in approximately 68% of affected patients [19]. The clinical presentation of these lesions is highly variable.

The types of reported oral manifestations include [19, 20]:

Ulcerations: Aphthous-like ulcers (canker sores) are among the most frequently described lesions. They can be single or multiple, appearing on non-keratinized mucosa.

Vesiculobullous Lesions: Herpetiform lesions, vesicles, and bullae have been reported, sometimes resembling conditions like herpes simplex or angina bullosa hemorrhagica.

Macules and Papules: Erythematous macules, papules, and plaques, sometimes described as Kawasaki-like or erythema multiforme-like, have been observed, particularly on the palate and tongue.

Tongue Alterations: A fissured or depapillated tongue ("COVID tongue") has been widely reported, characterized by loss of lingual papillae, leading to a smooth, bald appearance. Swelling and erythema are also common.

Vascular Lesions: Petechiae (small red or purple spots), hemorrhagic crusts, and signs of vasculitis or thrombosis have been noted, reflecting the coagulopathy associated with severe COVID-19.

Other Findings: Candidiasis (oral thrush), necrotizing periodontal disease, halitosis, and spontaneous gingival bleeding have also been linked to COVID-19, often as secondary phenomena related to immunosuppression, poor oral hygiene in hospitalized patients, or stress [19, 28].

The severity and extent of these oral lesions appear to correlate with the overall severity of COVID-19, with older patients and those with more severe systemic disease exhibiting more widespread lesions [19].

Neurostomatological syndromes and chemosensory dysfunction. Neurological manifestations with a direct link to the stomatognathic system are a hallmark of COVID-19 infection. The most prominent of these are chemosensory disturbances.

Dysgeusia and anosmia. Dysgeusia (taste alteration) and ageusia (complete loss of taste) are among the most frequently reported neurological symptoms of COVID-19, often occurring alongside anosmia (loss of smell) [11, 21]. One review identified dysgeusia as the first recognized oral symptom of the disease [19]. Their prevalence varies widely across studies but is consistently high, particularly in mild to moderate cases. Some studies suggest these symptoms can be important markers for COVID-19 infection, sometimes appearing as the sole initial manifestation [22]. The loss of taste is not merely a consequence of a blocked nose; it is considered a distinct neurological symptom. Patients often describe a diminished ability to perceive sweet, sour, bitter, or salty tastes, or a persistent metallic or foul taste.

Other neurological manifestations. While less common than chemosensory dysfunction, other neurostomatological syndromes have been reported. These include:

Facial Nerve Palsy: Cases of central and peripheral facial palsy, leading to weakness or paralysis of facial muscles, have been documented [29].

Neuralgia: Some patients report trigeminal neuralgia-like symptoms, characterized by sharp, shooting facial pain.

Burning Mouth Syndrome: A sensation of burning in the mouth without any visible lesions has been described as a post-COVID symptom.

Headache and Myalgia: Headache is one of the most common neurological symptoms overall (prevalence ~9.5-13.6%) [3, 13], and myalgia affecting the muscles of mastication can also occur, leading to facial pain and difficulty chewing.

Pathophysiological mechanisms. The mechanisms underlying these oral and neurostomatological manifestations are complex and likely multifactorial.

1. Direct Viral Invasion: The high expression of ACE2 receptors in the oral mucosa, particularly on the tongue and in salivary glands, provides a direct route for SARS-CoV-2 to infect host cells [17, 18]. This can lead to direct cellular damage, inflammation, and the clinical lesions observed. Viral replication in salivary glands may also explain the presence of viral RNA in saliva and contribute to hyposalivation. For chemosensory dysfunction, the virus may directly infect sustentacular (support) cells and stem cells within the olfactory epithelium and taste buds, which also express ACE2 and TMPRSS2 [16, 30].

2. Systemic Inflammation and Cytokine Storm: The severe inflammatory response seen in many COVID-19 patients can cause systemic effects that manifest in the oral cavity. Pro-inflammatory cytokines can increase vascular permeability, leading to edema, erythema, and potentially vesiculobullous lesions [16]. This systemic inflammation is a key driver of endothelial damage.

3. Vasculitis and Coagulopathy: COVID-19 is associated with endothelial dysfunction, hypercoagulability, and both micro- and macro-thrombosis [9]. This can lead to ischemic or thrombotic events in the small blood vessels of the oral mucosa, resulting in purpuric lesions, necrosis, and ulcerations that resemble vasculitis [19].

4. Immunosuppression and Opportunistic Infections: Severe illness, corticosteroid treatment, and the lymphopenia associated with COVID-19 can compromise the host's immune system. This creates an environment conducive to opportunistic infections, such as oral candidiasis or the reactivation of latent viruses like Herpes Simplex Virus (HSV), which can cause lesions that are secondary to the primary COVID-19 infection [19, 28].

5. Drug-Related Reactions: Some oral lesions may be adverse reactions to medications used in the treatment of COVID-19, presenting as drug-induced stomatitis or erythema multiforme-like eruptions [19].

Discussion. This systematized review of the literature confirms that the oral cavity is a frequent and significant site of COVID-19 pathology, with manifestations ranging from specific mucosal lesions to debilitating neurostomatological syndromes. The findings highlight the truly multisystemic nature of SARS-CoV-2 infection and underscore the importance of a comprehensive clinical examination that includes the oral and maxillofacial region [5, 31].

The prevalence and variety of oral lesions reported are striking. The identification of the tongue, labial mucosa, and palate as primary sites of involvement aligns with the known distribution of ACE2 receptors in

the oral cavity, supporting the hypothesis of direct viral invasion as a key pathogenic mechanism [17, 19]. The aphthous-like ulcers, herpetiform vesicles, and vascular lesions described are not entirely specific to COVID-19 and can mimic other viral or autoimmune conditions. This diagnostic challenge requires clinicians to maintain a high index of suspicion for COVID-19, especially when these lesions appear in conjunction with other systemic symptoms or known exposure [20]. The term "COVID tongue," while not a formal diagnosis, has effectively raised public and professional awareness of tongue-related changes like depapillation and swelling as potential signs of infection.

Perhaps the most clinically significant neurostomatological finding is the high incidence of dysgeusia and anosmia. Their frequent appearance as early, and sometimes isolated, symptoms positions them as valuable diagnostic red flags [21, 22]. This has critical public health implications, as individuals experiencing sudden taste or smell loss should be advised to self-isolate and seek testing, even in the absence of respiratory symptoms. The neurological basis of these symptoms—damage to chemosensory cells and their neural pathways rather than simple nasal congestion—is a crucial distinction that points to the neurotropic capabilities of SARS-CoV-2 [16]. While most cases of chemosensory dysfunction resolve, a subset of patients experiences persistent symptoms, contributing to the constellation of "Long COVID" and impacting quality of life through altered nutrition and enjoyment of food [12].

The pathophysiological mechanisms elucidated in this review—direct viral entry, systemic inflammation, vasculopathy, and secondary infections—create a cohesive model for understanding how a respiratory virus can cause such diverse oral and neurological effects [16, 19, 30]. The interplay between these factors likely determines the specific clinical presentation in an individual patient. For instance, a patient with a strong inflammatory response and underlying vascular risk factors may be more prone to thrombotic oral lesions, while an immunosuppressed patient may be more likely to develop secondary oral candidiasis [9, 19]. This multifactorial etiology complicates treatment, which must be tailored to the underlying cause, whether it involves antiviral therapy, anti-inflammatory agents, or management of secondary infections.

This review has several limitations inherent to the available literature. Many of the initial reports were case studies or small case series, which are subject to selection bias and may overrepresent more severe or unusual presentations [24]. The prevalence data for oral lesions vary widely, partly due to a lack of systematic oral examinations in many early COVID-19 treatment protocols. As the pandemic progressed, awareness grew, but standardized reporting is still lacking. Furthermore, distinguishing primary COVID-19 lesions from secondary manifestations (e.g., opportunistic infections, drug reactions) can be challenging without histopathological or virological confirmation from the lesion itself, which was not always performed.

In conclusion, the evidence strongly supports the inclusion of oral and neurostomatological manifestations as key features in the clinical spectrum of COVID-19. These symptoms are not mere curiosities but are clinically relevant phenomena with diagnostic, prognostic, and therapeutic implications. Healthcare professionals, particularly dentists and oral medicine specialists, play a vital role in identifying these signs, managing patient symptoms, and contributing to a broader understanding of this complex disease. Future research should focus on large-scale, prospective cohort studies with standardized oral examination protocols to establish more precise prevalence rates and to further investigate the long-term oral and neurological sequelae of COVID-19.

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